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The moderating role of resilience in the relationship between marital stress and depression

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Abstract

The study investigated the moderating role of resilience in the relationship between marital stress and depression among married teachers, with one hundred thirty-five (135) married teachers that comprises of 102 females and 33 males with an age mean of 32.20 and S.D 3.81 selected as participants using multi-stage (cluster, simple: balloting, and purposive) sampling techniques. Zung (1965) Self-rating Depression Scale (SDS), Omoluabi (1994) marital stress Inventory (MSI) and Connor and Davidson (2003). Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC) were used for data collection, a cross-sectional survey design was adopted, while a moderated hierarchical multiple regression was used for data analysis. The finding shows that marital stress $St = .551^{***}$ and $t = 7.608^{***}$ at $p < .001$ positively predicted depression, Resilience $St = -.517^{***}$ and $t = -6.962^{***}$ at $p < .001$ negatively predicted depression among school teachers and Resilience $St = -.748^{***}$ and $t = -7.178^{***}$ at $p < .001$ negatively moderated the relationship between marital stress and depression. Hence, school management can consider hiring psychologists to work with teachers to improve their resilience or educate them on the importance of resilience in managing depression.

Keywords

Resilience, marital stress, depression, married, secondary school, teachers.

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Introduction

Depression constitutes a formidable contributor to global health loss. In 2015, it was estimated that depression caused over 50 million years of disability worldwide (World Health Organization, 2017). Apart from being a mental health concern, depression also elevates the risk of premature death and several physical ailments (Herlofson *et al.*, 2016). It is imperative to raise awareness about depression, develop preventive measures, and provide effective treatment options to curb its impact. It has been established that work-related stress is a significant risk factor for depression, and the teaching profession appears to be particularly susceptible to this problem (Herlofson *et al.*, 2016; Arvidsson *et al.*, 2016; Wieclaw *et al.*, 2005). The high quantitative and emotional demands placed on teachers are likely contributing factors to this phenomenon (Arvidsson *et al.*, 2016; Wieclaw *et al.*, 2005). Therefore, there is a pressing need to explore the potential role of resilience in mitigating marital stress and predicting depression among school teachers.

Depression, as a psychological concept, refers to a mood or emotional state characterized by a reduced ability to enjoy life and feelings of low self-worth or guilt (Rodriguez, 2022). Individuals experiencing depression typically exhibit various symptoms, including but not limited to sadness, hopelessness, or pessimism, reduced self-esteem, decreased interest in activities, diminished energy levels, slow thoughts or actions, loss of appetite, and sleep disturbances or insomnia (Rodriguez, 2022). It is important to differentiate depression from normal grief or mourning, which are appropriate emotional responses to the loss of loved ones or valued objects. In cases where there are identifiable reasons for a person's unhappiness, depression is deemed to be present when the duration or severity of the depressed mood is disproportionately high relative to the precipitating event (Rodriguez, 2022). These distinctions in terms of duration, circumstances, and other associated characteristics form the basis for categorizing depression into various types (Rodriguez, 2022).

The trajectory of depression varies significantly from one individual to another and can manifest in different forms, ranging from mild to severe, acute to chronic. If left untreated, depression can persist for an average period of four months or even longer. It is noteworthy that depression is twice as common in women as in men, as per Britannica (2023). Although the typical age of onset is in the 20s, depression may occur at any point in an individual's life. Depression can arise from a variety of causes. Adverse life events can heighten an individual's susceptibility to depression or incite a depressive episode (Rodriguez, 2022). Negative self-perception and a pessimistic outlook on the world are also significant factors in the genesis and perpetuation of depressive symptoms. Moreover, individuals who are exposed to chronic stress or have a history of traumatic experiences, such as childhood abuse or neglect, may be at a higher risk of developing depression. Unfortunately, depression may create a cycle of stress and dysfunction, exacerbating the affected person's overall life situation and the condition itself. Marital stress is among the factors that may contribute to depression in married individuals.

According to Patterson (2020), marital stress can be defined as a state of negative effects, such as frustration and anxiety that arise from various aspects of the marriage. Such stress can result from differences in religious beliefs, cultural backgrounds, social statuses, educational gaps, age gaps, and work statuses, as well as varying coping strategies. All of these challenges may lead to marital stress (Nwatu, 2018). Dave (2018) identified financial stress as the most common cause of stress in marriage, and it is often cited as the primary reason for divorce. As noted by Scott (2022), the stress of arguing over money is commonly cited as one of the most prevalent problems faced by married couples. However, during tough economic periods, financial stress can also engender more generalized stress, conflicts over non-financial issues, as well as money-centred arguments. For

instance, when one partner is severely stressed about finances, they may exhibit less patience and heightened stress levels in general, leading them to engage in arguments with their partner over unrelated matters without realizing it (Scott, 2022).

The journey of parenthood is a precious one, filled with the joys of nurturing children and building a fulfilling family life. However, as Scott (2022) has pointed out, it can also be a source of strain and challenges for couples. The increased obligations and shifts in roles that accompany caring for a child can create added stress within a relationship, leading to conflicts and tensions. While children can undoubtedly bring immense blessings to a family, they also require thoughtful navigation through the unique obstacles they present (Scott, 2022). Having children can indeed bring about unique challenges to a marriage. As Scott (2022) has pointed out, the added responsibilities and changes in roles can create stress and conflicts within a relationship. It can also reduce the time available for bonding as a couple, which can test even the strongest of bonds (Scott, 2022). Additionally, raising children can be a significant financial burden that, if not handled properly, can lead to stress in a marriage (Dave, 2018). Merging two families can also be challenging, as creating healthy boundaries and dynamics with in-laws may not always be easy (Dave, 2018). Despite these challenges, though, many couples find that the joys of parenthood and the rewards of a close-knit family are worth the effort.

Parenthood is a journey that is both precious and challenging. As Scott (2022) posits, introducing children into a marriage can lead to increased obligations and shifts in roles that can create added stress within a relationship, leading to conflicts and tensions. This can also reduce the amount of time available for bonding as a couple and test even the strongest of bonds (Scott, 2022). Furthermore, raising children can be a significant financial burden that, if not handled properly, can lead to stress in a marriage (Dave, 2018). Merging two families can also be challenging, as creating healthy boundaries and dynamics with in-laws may not always be easy (Dave, 2018).

Effective communication is essential in a marriage as miscommunication can result in marital stress (Dave, 2018). Sexual frustration is another source of stress in a marriage, as it takes more than just sex to build a strong and healthy relationship. Without it, a couple may experience tension and frustration (Dave, 2018). Work stress is also a common factor that can bring stress into the home. Many couples spend more time at work than at home, and a stressful work situation can negatively impact a marriage (Dave, 2018). Couples must recognize these potential stressors and work together to find ways to manage them to maintain a healthy and strong relationship. According to Scott (2022), daily stressors can exacerbate existing problems in a marriage, although they do not necessarily lead to issues. When one partner experiences a stressful day, it may cause them to be more impatient, handle conflicts less expertly, and have less emotional energy to devote to nurturing their relationship. This can hurt the relationship. When both partners have had a challenging day, the impact can be even more severe (Scott, 2022). Couples need to recognize the effects of daily stressors on their relationship and work together to manage them to prevent them from causing further strain on their marriage.

Overly busy schedules can lead to marriage problems for several reasons, as Scott (2022) has posited. Couples who lead busy lives are often stressed, particularly if they are not taking care of themselves through quality sleep and good nutrition. This stress can hurt their relationship. Additionally, busy couples may feel less connected because they have less time to spend together and more separateness in their lives (Scott, 2022).

As Ben (2021) has postulated, resilience is a crucial trait in managing stressful situations. Couples who are resilient are better able to manage their responses to stress and prevent being overwhelmed

by it. Busy couples need to recognize the potential impact of their schedules on their relationship take steps to manage their stress levels and prioritize time spent together to maintain a strong and healthy marriage. As Ben (2021) has pointed out, individuals manage their stress in different ways, but those who are resilient will have strategies to help them through challenging times. Bradley and Hojjat (2017) have theorized that resilience can serve as a buffer in the relationship between marital stress and depression as well as other relevant variables. This suggests that more resilient individuals may be better equipped to handle the stressors that come with marriage and maintain a healthy relationship. Couples need to recognize the significance of resilience in marriage and develop strategies to help them manage stress and overcome challenges for a stronger and more resilient relationship.

As de Terte and Stephens (2014) define, resilience is the ability to cope with a crisis or to return to pre-crisis status quickly. This suggests that resilient individuals are better equipped to manage stress and overcome challenging situations. Moreover, Robertson *et al.*, (2015) have posited that resilience exists when individuals use mental processes and behaviours to promote personal assets and protect themselves from the potential negative effects of stressors. In essence, resilient individuals can utilize their resources to navigate through difficult times and maintain their well-being. Understanding the concept of resilience is crucial for individuals in maintaining a healthy and sustainable lifestyle, particularly in the context of a marriage where stressors are an inevitable part of life. Psychological resilience pertains to the capacity of individuals to develop psychological and behavioural capabilities that enable them to remain composed during crises or chaos and to recover from the incident without enduring negative long-term consequences. Ehrich *et al.*, (2017) posit that resilience is a psychological trait characterized by positive adaptation that empowers individuals to respond effectively to stressful situations. In essence, resilient individuals are better equipped to confront the challenges that life presents and rebound from difficult experiences. Understanding the concept of resilience is of utmost importance for individuals in preserving their well-being and managing the stressors that arise in life, including those that may impinge on their relationships and marriages.

There is a common misconception that resilient individuals are free from negative emotions or thoughts and remain optimistic in most or all situations. However, as Chen *et al.*, (2018) have pointed out, resilience plays an important protective role against psychopathology, and both positive and negative coping strategies can affect both resilience and mental health. In essence, people who demonstrate resilience are individuals with an optimistic attitude and positive emotionality, who can effectively balance negative emotions with positive ones through practice. Understanding the nuances of resilience is essential for individuals to maintain their mental health and well-being, particularly in the context of a marriage where stressors can impact the relationship. It is important to recognize that resilience is not merely about overcoming a deeply stressful situation, but also about emerging from it with competent functioning. Oshioa *et al.*, (2018) state that resilience is the process of being able to adapt well and bounce back quickly in times of stress. However, resilience or psychological resilience (Bonanno *et al.*, 2015) is a complex construct that encompasses traits, outcomes, and processes related to recovery, and, thus, it has been defined differently in the context of individuals, families, organizations, societies, and cultures (Oshioa *et al.*, 2018). In essence, resilience involves not only the ability to cope with stress but also the capacity to recover and adapt, which is crucial for individuals in maintaining their well-being and managing the stressors that come their way, including those that may impact their relationships and marriages.

Research has shown that individuals who possess high levels of resilience are more likely to be competent and comfortable in the often-unclear interpersonal world (Oshioa, *et al.*, 2018). Conversely, individuals with low levels of resilience may act in a stiff and preservative manner or

chaotically and diffusely when confronted with stressful circumstances, resulting in maladaptive behaviour (Oshioa, et al., 2018). By taking a typological approach, the literature has identified three basic personality types: ego-resilient, vulnerable over-controllers, and unsettled under-controllers (Oshioa, et al., 2018). Understanding the different types of resilience is important for individuals in maintaining their well-being and managing the stressors that come their way. By identifying their personality type, individuals can develop strategies to build resilience and cope more effectively with stressful situations, including those that may arise in the context of a marriage or relationship.

According to Xue (2020), daily stressors can disrupt an individual's internal and external sense of balance, presenting both challenges and opportunities. However, routine stressors of daily life can also have positive impacts that promote resilience. The appropriate level of stress for each individual is still unknown, as some people can handle greater amounts of stress than others (Xue, 2020). Moreover, psychological resilience can influence cognitive biases through multiple factors and its intermediary role in the regulation of positive emotions (Xue, 2020). Individuals need to understand the role of resilience in managing stress and promoting well-being, particularly in the context of a marriage or relationship. By developing strategies to build resilience and manage stress, individuals can better cope with the challenges that they face and maintain a healthy and strong relationship.

The cognitive theory developed by Beck (1967), is used as a theoretical framework because it emphasizes an individual's belief system rather than their behaviour. The theory posits that the meaning individuals give to events holds significant importance, as a positive interpretation can lead to less stressful situations, while a negative one can result in depression. Resilience, too, is a mental state, as motivation and belief in one's ability to recover from setbacks can help individuals manage stress and avoid depression. For teachers, this is especially important in their role, as maintaining a positive mindset can help to cushion against depression and enable them to perform their jobs effectively. Understanding the cognitive theory of depression and building resilience is essential for individuals in maintaining their mental health and well-being, including those who are in a marriage or relationship. Hence the hypotheses:

- I. Marital stress will predict depression among school teachers
- II. Resilience will predict depression among school teachers
- III. Resilience will moderate the relationship between marital stress and depression among school teachers

METHOD

Participants

One hundred and thirty-five (135) married teachers comprising 102 females and 33 males with age mean of 32.20 and S.D 3.81 were drawn as participants using multi-stage (cluster, simple: balloting and purposive) sampling techniques: thirty from Station primary school (30) Agbani, ten from Central primary school 1 (10), fifteen Central primary school 2 (15), ten from wisdom kids nursery and primary school (10), twelve from Aliens comprehensive secondary school Agbani (12), twenty-three Mater comprehensive school Agbani (23), twenty-four from St Joseph comprehensive secondary school Agbani (24), and eleven from Holy Family (11) all in Nkanu West Local Government Area of Enugu State.

Instrument

These set of instruments were used:

- Zung (1965) Self-rating Depression Scale (SDS)
- Omoluabi (1994) Marital stress inventory (MSI) and
- Connor and Davidson (2003). Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC)

Self-rating Depression Scale

Zung (1965) Self-rating Depression Scale was developed to measure depression as a clinical disorder. It is a 20-item inventory that is designed to assess the cognitive, affective, psychomotor, somatic and social interpersonal dimensions of depression. It is scored directly by adding together the values of the numbers shaded in all the 20 items to give you the mean score. The normative cut-off point or mean scores established by Zung (1965) in categorizing the participants where the level of depression are thus; 50 – 59 = mild depression, 60 – 69 = moderate depression, 70 – 80 = severe depression. For the Nigeria sample, the norms obtained by Obiora (1995) with a population of secondary school students for male and female are 48.77 and 47.87 respectively. A coefficient of concurrent validity of .79 was obtained by Zung (1965), a three-day interval test-retest coefficient of reliability of .93 was obtained by Obiora (1995), between SDS and Hamilton rating scale (HRS) Hamilton (1960) between SDS and the depression scale of MMPI, the coefficient of .70 was obtained.

Omoluabi (1994) Marital stress inventory (MSI)

Omoluabi (1994) marital stress inventory (MSI) is a 50-item inventory that is a list of issues that cause disaffection in a marriage. It is designed to help clinical/counselling psychologists determine the specific causes of marital discord and distress among their clients. Add together the values of the numbers shaded in all the terms. Omoluabi (1994) provided the psychometric properties for the Nigerian samples. The norms reported here are the mean scores obtained by the general population. $M(n=275) = 77.83$, $F(n=282) = 74.49$ $M\&F(n=557) = 76.20$. Cronbach alpha coefficient = .9219, Spearman brown split half, coefficient = .9238, Gutman split-half coefficient = .9226, Beta coefficient = .9639. A concurrent validity coefficient of .32 was obtained by correlating MSI with the marital satisfaction index (MSI) by Hunson (1982).

The norms or mean scores as the basis for interpreting the scores of clients. Scores higher than the norms indicate high-stress levels or reactions and general unhappiness with the marriage. Scores lower than the norms indicate that the clients are coping adequately with existing stressors in the marriage. Items rated 4 or 5 by the client indicate the specific causes of stress for the client such items should be the focus of psychotherapy/counselling with the client.

Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC)

Connor and Davidson (2003) Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale; CD-RISC measures the level of resilience of an individual, the CD-RISC consists of 25 items which are evaluated on a five-point Likert form scale ranging from 0-4; not true at all (0), rarely true (1), sometimes true (2), often true (3), and true nearly all of the time (4) – these ratings result in a number between 0-100, and higher scores indicate higher resilience.

Cronbach's α for CD-RISC was 0.97. CD-RISC was associated with depressive symptoms ($r = -0.18$), family harmony ($r = 0.20$), family functioning ($r = 0.27$) and was not associated with alcohol consumption ($r = 0.05$). The mean score for the CD-RISC is 59.99 (SD = 13.92). Men, younger individuals, and those with higher education or higher household income reported higher resilience levels.

Procedures

The researcher adopted multi-stage (cluster, simple: by balloting and purposive) sampling techniqueto draw participants: the selected schools all in Nkanu West Local Government Area of Enugu State. The researcher employed the help of research assistants who are National Youth Service Corp Members serving in the selected schools to administer and retrieve the instrument. The participants who are school teachers were selected with the aid of availability sampling techniques; the schools that accepted the researcher's request to carry out the study with staff and teachers who agreed to participate were selected, and then the selected ones were asked to respond to the items by shading one of the boxes in front of the statements which best reflects what degree they agree or disagree with the statement. One hundred and forty-two (142) copies of the questionnaire were distributed, and one hundred and thirty-eight (138) copies were returned of which four (4) were wrongly responded to and were discarded, which sums up the numbers well responded to be one hundred and thirty-five (135), which were used for data analysis..

Design and Statistics

Correlational design was adopted based on the fact that the researcher is investigating the level of interaction of resilience on marital stress and how it can predict depression. The statistical test that was used for data analysis is moderated hierarchical multiple regression using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Version 25 software. Thus, Means and standard deviation distributions will be investigated. These will help to determine the direction and strength of the relationships among the study variables, as well as the moderating role (George, 2008).

Result

Table 1: descriptive statistics

S/N	Variables	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1	Depression	41.60	8.66	1	.551**	.182	-.517**	-.144	-.080	.343**	-.409**
2	Marital stress	142.93	39.04		1	.806***	-.088	.090	.073	.135	.244**
3	moderator	9167.6	3940.05			1	.513**	.362**	.245*	.060	.516**
4	Resilience	64.53	16.512				1	.440**	.340**	-.122	.540**
5	age	32.20	3.812					1	-.445**	-.245**	.243**
6	gender	1.73	.4438						1	.064	.472**
7	Educational Qualification	2.33	.7917							1	.056
8	Years of experience	4.33	2.029								1

Table 1 above shows that depression and resilience are negatively correlated at $r = -.517$, which implies that an increase in resilience will cause a decrease in depression among married teachers. Table 1 shows that depression and marital stress are positively related at $r = .551$, this means that the increase in marital stress will cause an increase in depression among married teachers. At the same time, depression and resilience moderating marital stress are not to be related at $r = .183$. Depression is shown to be positively related to educational qualification at $r = .343$, which implies that the increase in educational qualification among married teachers will cause an increase in depression. Years of

experience and depression at $r = -.409$ indicated a negative correlation, which implies that the increase in years of experience will cause a decrease in depression. Marital stress at $r = .244$ is positively related to years of experience, this indicates an increase in years of experience will cause an increase in marital stress among school teachers.

Table 2: regression statistics

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	UnSt	St	t
1	.551***	.303***	.298***			
Marital stress				.122***	.551***	7.608***
2	.706***	.499***	.491***			
moderator				-.002***	-.748***	-7.178***
3	.914***	.836***	.827***			
Resilience				-.271***	-.517***	-6.962***
age				1.315***	.578***	7.958***
gender				12.117***	.621***	9.385***
Educational Qualification				3.925***	.359***	8.647***
Years of experience				-3.116***	-.730***	-13.349***

Dependent variable= depression, at $p < .05^*$, $p < .01^{**}$, at $p < .001^{***}$. $r =$ relationship, $r^2 =$ relationship square, UnSt= unstandardised, St= standardised

Table 2 above shows that marital stress $St = .551^{***}$ and $t = 7.608^{***}$ at $p < .001$ positively predicted depression among school teachers, this indicates an increase in marital stress will cause an increase in depression, and marital stress contributed 30.3% variance to depression at $r^2 = .302$.

Resilience $St = -.748^{***}$ and $t = -7.178^{***}$ at $p < .001$ negatively moderated the relationship between marital stress and depression, this implies that the presence of resilience in marital stress will cause a decrease in depression among school teachers. The moderating variable is shown to be related to depression at $r = .706$, and it contributes 50% variation in depression among school teachers at $r^2 = .499$.

Resilience $St = -.517^{***}$ and $t = -6.962^{***}$ at $p < .001$ negatively predicted depression among school teachers, indicate that the presence of resilience will cause the absence of depression.

Discussion

The first hypothesis tested which stated marital stress will significantly predict depression among secondary school teachers was confirmed. The results of this study show that stress in marriages can lead to an increased risk of depression among married couples. The findings suggest that stressful marital situations can increase the likelihood of developing depression, particularly among married teachers. Marital stress is one of the most commonly encountered and distressing human problems, and its impact on mental health and well-being cannot be overstated. Understanding the relationship between stress in marriages and depression is crucial for individuals, particularly those who are married or in a relationship. By recognizing the potential impact of marital stress on mental health, individuals can take steps to manage stressors and prevent them from causing further harm to their relationships and overall well-being.

The second hypothesis tested which stated that resilience will predict depression among married primary school teachers was confirmed. The results obtained are in line with the work of Vandelanotte, Cope, et al. (2022), which posits that resilience is a crucial factor in determining the likelihood of developing depression. The findings suggest that a lack of resilience can lead to

depression, as resilience is an inherent characteristic or ability of individuals to bounce back from stressful situations. When teachers lack resilience or their resilience levels decline, they may not be able to withstand normal pressures, which can lead to depression. Understanding the role of resilience in mental health is crucial for individuals, particularly those who are married or in a relationship. By developing strategies to build resilience and manage stress, individuals can better cope with the challenges of daily life and prevent them from causing further harm to their mental health and relationships.

The third hypothesis tested which stated that resilience will moderate marital stress as a prediction of depression among married teachers was confirmed. The results of the study suggest that resilience is a crucial factor in managing marital stress and reducing the risk of depression. The findings indicate that resilience can moderate the effects of marital stress on depression, meaning that increasing resilience can help to mitigate the impact of marital stress. Resilience is a variable that assists individuals in bouncing back from stressful situations, and it can help teachers in managing their stress levels and developing coping mechanisms to address depression. By building resilience, individuals can better manage marital stress and prevent it from leading to depression, ultimately promoting better mental health and well-being.

Implication of the findings

The findings of the study are consistent with the cognitive theory of (Beck, 1967), which was used as the theoretical framework. The theory emphasizes an individual's belief system rather than their behaviour and postulates that the meaning individuals give to events is crucial. A positive interpretation can lead to a less stressful situation, while a negative one can result in depression. Resilience, too, is a mental state, as motivation and belief in one's ability to recover from setbacks can help individuals manage stress and avoid depression. For teachers, this is especially important in their role, as maintaining a positive mindset can help to cushion against depression and enable them to perform their jobs effectively. Understanding the cognitive theory of depression and building resilience is essential for individuals in maintaining their mental health and well-being, including those who are in a marriage or relationship.

The results of this study suggest that marital stress is a key predictor of depression, and resilience can play a moderating role in reducing the impact of marital stress on depression among teachers. As such, clinicians should work to assist married teachers who seek treatment to develop higher levels of resilience, as this can help to manage marital stress and prevent depression. School management can also play a role in reducing teacher depression by working to ensure that teachers' qualifications and rank or salary are equivalent, which can reduce stress levels. Additionally, school management can consider hiring psychologists to work with teachers to improve their resilience or educate them on the importance of resilience in managing depression. Finally, it may be beneficial to recruit teachers at a younger age to provide them with a longer duration of service and help them build resilience over time. By implementing these strategies, we can work to manage the impact of marital stress on depression among teachers and promote better mental health and well-being in the teaching profession.

Limitations of the study

Many factors worked against this research work, and the major one is the indiscriminate call for sitting at home in the southeast which reduces the number of working days, as this study was carried out when there were frequent calls for sitting at home by non-state authors. The researcher would have drawn more participants assuming there was no continued unnecessary call for sit at home.

Insecurity was another factor, the issue of unknown gunmen increased fear among the populace who were sceptical about the researcher's intention even after much enlightenment. More participants would have been selected assuming no insecurity-induced fear of the unknown.

The sudden increase in inflation which leads to a sharp increase in goods and services also affected this work, because it affected the researcher's budget.

Suggestions for further study

The future researcher should try to sample participants from another geo-political region where there are no indiscriminate calls for sit at home, to give room for more participants.

The use of third parties to reach the participants should be looked at by the future researcher. To give confidence of secrecy and safety to the participants, this will increase the numbers that will participate.

A few locations should be considered also by future researchers to accommodate the budget in case there is inflation.

Summary and conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, it can be inferred that an increase in resilience can lead to a decrease in depression among married primary school teachers. Additionally, the study highlights that marital stress is a significant contributor to depression among married primary school teachers. The results also suggest that resilience negatively moderates the effect of marital stress on depression, indicating that the presence of resilience can help to mitigate the impact of marital stress on depression among married primary school teachers. Overall, the findings underscore the importance of promoting resilience as a means to reduce depression and manage marital stress among married primary school teachers.

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